

REVOLUTIONS AND COMMON FRAMES

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INTRODUCTION

Social base with full awareness politically active with a clear organization and project, it does not exist as such but there are a number of sectors that are still aware, imbued by the ideas of the end of the century and a large social base without concreteness. They will be revolutions backed by bourgeois intellectuals and by certain sectors of the army, authentic minorities. These revolutionaries are aware that they are the only educated sector that can promote change, that they have to work for a great ignorant uneducated mass, that cannot know what is convenient. Strongly united in the belief that these principles can be exported to the entire continent (internationalism), exile playing a strong role.

The repression carried out by the restoration causes specific sectors to go into political exile (Spain, Ferdinand VII - Exile Liberals, Poland, Italy or Germany). They maintain a close relationship between them and their places of origin, consequently the path of the secret Brotherhoods will be used, whose origin is found in FREEMASONRY, although now they will take on another aspect and importance. Precisely because we are talking about minority groups, weak and harassed by the repressive structure of the restoration, a way of self-defense and articulation of conspiracies that will spread throughout the continent - Vertebration of a determined character.

The revolutions of 1930 will not be so internationalist precisely because of nationalism, they will not be so minority or interconnected. Therefore, they lose vigor.

The revolutions of 1820 will be called MEDITERRANEAN REVOLUTIONS, the 3 peninsulas of the Mediterranean will be affected by the revolutionary movements of this cycle, original revolutions (years 20 and 21).

- The movements will begin in the German environment, although it is not a revolutionary process specifically, but in a marked concern that come from intellectual sectors of the German university, demanding greater freedoms and rights, a more flexible framework. These demands were the portico of the revolutions of this period, quickly subdued by the rapid and effective intervention of CHANCELLOR METTERNICH, he drowns that concern, and also initiates the process of successive congresses aimed at intervening in international processes, whenever liberal revolutionary processes or movements appear. on an international level.
- • SPAIN: Pronouncement of General RIEGO, reinstatement of the Cadiz Constitution (1812), LIBERAL TRIENNium, led by the army, but supported by sectors of the bourgeoisie, all of them had failed. Riego's triumphs because it was the only one that got enough popular support. The previous ones had remained in the dome, exclusively the army.
- In the year 1823 a new congress decides to send troops (French) to replace the absolute monarchical order.
- • ITALIAN PENINSULA: Demonstrations take place both in the North (Piedmont) and in the South (Naples), of a Carbonario nature. At first they will succeed, but they will end up failing due to the intervention of Austrian troops.
- • FRANCE: Assassination of the Duke of BERRY, possible heir to the French crown, and the uprising of some of the country's military garrisons. It failed possibly due to lack of structuring of the various movements basically due to lack of sufficient social support - POLITICAL ACTION.

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- • GREECE: Country that is subject to the Turkish Empire. It is a country where the revolution acquires a double character: on the one hand, independence from the empire is sought (liberal character); on the other hand construction of a sovereign country (national character). The revolution in Greece is the only one in this entire cycle that we can qualify as a genuine mass revolution. In addition, the circumstance that European diplomacy is favorable to this process, for this reason they will not only not intervene but will also support the movement. It is, therefore, an example for emerging nationalisms, which will gain strength over time.
- LATE EPILOGUE - DECEMBRIST MOVEMENT: Occurs in December 1825, taking place in Russia at the death of Tsar Alexander I. Taking advantage of this situation, the implementation in this country of a liberal - constitutional system is proposed. It will not take effect because his successor, Nicholas I will maintain the iron structure implanted in Russia. However, although it failed, we must not forget that it signifies the beginning of the Russian movement that will lead to 1917. Only one revolution has triumphed, the others have been subdued and the monarchies of the Old Regime remain practically intact.
- BETWEEN 1820 AND 1830: Certain moments and factors will occur that will determine the revolutionary cycle of 1830.
- Relatively important economic changes will take place in certain countries. That is to say, continental Europe is beginning to experience a certain industrial-technological development, especially in France and Belgium.
- Economic recovery. Some things have begun to change, we find ourselves with certain middle sectors that are beginning to have their own concerns, thus joining those of the bourgeoisie. Of course, being closely related to the situation of each country. The way of the brotherhoods loses validity, because it is a broader movement, that is, it covers more sectors, it is not so restricted.
- 1830: The revolutions of this decade marked an important turning point in the process.
- FRANCE: Start this cycle. It is one of the countries where the political and social changes are more important, where and in return the restored monarchy, by the hand of CARLOS X, wants to take a new step backwards by limiting the system itself, reducing the few rights and freedoms that had been maintained through the JULY ORDINANCES. In this climate, they begin to express certain concerns that will lead to the overthrow of the Bourbon monarchy and implantation of LUIS FELIPE DE ORLERANS - MONARQUA BURGUESA. Triumph of bourgeois principles. • BELGIUM: This is one of the countries affected by the Vienna agreements. In 1815 Belgium becomes a dependent part of the Netherlands. There are many differentiating factors:
 - Religious: While the Netherlands has a Protestant majority, Belgium is Catholic.
 - Economy: It is more developed in Belgium.
 - Existence of a nation seed that had been highlighted in the eighteenth century.
 - It will achieve its objectives by achieving independence from the Netherlands and establishing a monarchy - LEOPOLD I - with a constitutional system.
- ITALY: This time it's up to the central zone of the peninsula, but the movement will not bear fruit, maintaining the repressive system due to the intervention of the Austrian troops, aborting the liberal movements. However, certain societies will emerge, among them YOUNG ITALY, appearing intellectuals who advocate independence - MAZZINI. Precedent of independence which was achieved in the second half of the century.
- GERMANY: The ultimate or definitive objectives will not be achieved either, but also from now on, in some way led by Prussia, the process of liberalization and unification, starting from the customs union - ZOLLVEREIN. The movements that are reproduced in this decade will be the germ of unification.
- POLAND: Also affected by the remodeling of the map of Europe, a country that is constantly occupied, separated, divided. In 1815 it is subjected to Russia. A liberalization movement develops that will not achieve its objective.

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- NORDIC COUNTRIES.
- SPAIN AND PORTUGAL: Coinciding with this time, the death of the respective sovereigns took place and the beginning of a timid constitutionalism that would end up being implanted later. Contrasted by the Civil War that tries to maintain what is established (1833 - Carlist War / counterrevolution).

In 1830 there is, therefore, a division between Eastern and Western Europe. A significant group of countries have entered into a constitutional system, while in the East none have done so. The pace of evolution will be more dynamic in the western zone than in the eastern zone, where, above all, Russia will maintain its structures until the beginning of the 20th century.

BRITISH CASE: Emphasize once again, the different pace of evolution experienced in relation to the other countries of the Western world, specifically Europe.

England experienced a political revolution in the seventeenth century, which develops an advanced political system, throughout this century experienced a strong economic change - Industrial Revolution. Logically, it cannot present the same situation. Coinciding with the waves of the 1920s and 1930s, we find an embryonic labor movement (a pioneer in this field), which also begins to outline demands that in Europe will develop along two lines:

- Political Way: Claims regarding the political framework and participation and integration in that framework (Highlights the Chartist Movement - Collects and raises claims regarding suffrage)
- Via Trade Unions: Labor issues - Trade Unions.

3. THE REVOLUTION OF 1848:

It will practically close the cycle of bourgeois liberal revolutions (also called Atlantic revolutions). The long period of time from the first revolutions to this moment, the tensions, movements and upheavals. To what extent have things changed? In what sense?:

- The population has experienced a notable increase throughout this period.

- There has been a notable advance in urban planning, the development of large cities and the emergence of new ones.
- Development of internal and external communications making this world more affordable.
- Increases industrial production, growing to levels unthinkable until then.
- Greater wealth has been generated.
- The investigation will grow advancing in a positive way, etc. -.

But if we go inside, we will realize that under that positive appearance, there is enormous poverty and inequalities, which not only do not decrease but are growing more and more.

- SOCIAL CONTEXT: The vast majority of the population of Western countries continues to be a peasant, rural population linked directly or indirectly to agriculture. Only British society is about to exceed its urban population to the rural (it will be in 1851 when the urban population exceeds the rural population).

For legal purposes, slavery has disappeared (existence of restrictive laws) but nevertheless, there are still regions where not only do they not disappear but are expanding (Brazil, the South of the United States) where, as a consequence of the increase in the demand for raw materials is experiencing strong growth.

In addition, certain types of work considered as semi-slavery have been created. The servitude with respect to the feudal lord has been abolished in most of Europe except in Russia, this will lead directly to the peasant being freed for legal purposes, but not for economic purposes, a series of economic relations are developed that prevent the free development of these individuals. The real situation, therefore, has not improved, above all it is flagrant in countries with a tradition of landowners (in the case of Spain). The old manorial system was repressive and limited his freedoms, but he had some small compensations such as the enjoyment of communal lands and certain guarantees that he has now lost without finding anything in return.

During this decade we will not find true mobilizations of the peasantry, in the sense that there is no organized movement, with certain objectives against or against this situation (1880 - 1890).

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- **ECONOMIC CONTEXT:** Only England can qualify as an industrialized economy. However, in Europe the industrialization process has known a process of development and takeoff that will lead to certain consequences of this process that begin to worry certain intellectuals and leading sectors in the 1940s.
- Generates important benefits.
- A new model of society is being defined.

But there is a large sector that is not benefiting from that wealth (working class). He also feels outside this social model, lives in really precarious conditions, concentrated in the suburbs of cities - industrial belts. It is gradually degrading.

The domestic system gave work to a significant number of people and families, but the progressive and accelerated advance of machinery has put an end to that domestic system, placing the worker in that marginalized and displaced situation.

At the height of 1848 we still cannot find a concretion of the working class, non-existent except in England. We cannot speak of a labor movement that influences because it does not exist, since a coordinated project is lacking. We will find mobilizations of the working sectors, driven by hunger, deterioration and hatred caused by these situations.

Indeed, in many places in this period the model of aristocratic society has disappeared, it does not prevent the disappearance of the noble aristocracy, which continues to have an important weight, given the fact that the greatest fortunes are or belong to the great cotton planters in the United States. United States and British landowners.

Therefore, a symbiosis is produced, an interrelation between the old aristocracy and the new industrial, financial and commercial bourgeoisie (frequently sealed by marriages or purely economic relations). We find ourselves with a social design that continues to be a society of minorities in whose highest stratum is the old nobility and the new bourgeoisie.

Still the middle sectors do not constitute an authentic social force, being their relative weight still.

Minority, elitist society made up of a small minority with the greatest privileges derived from their wealth, weak middle sectors and a large mass made up of urban and rural population in a continuous process of degradation and poverty.

- **POLITICAL CONTEXT:** The monarchy is still the majority political system (except in those countries, especially Americans, where the revolutions introduced a republican system). Constitutional monarchies with a limited framework or in some countries permanence of absolute monarchies, going through a great variety of intermediate models. It is a legal framework designed for these elites and in no case for the social bases. The changes experienced, therefore, have not been so profound.

The reality before 1848 is a reality of enormous imbalances and inequalities, indeed we have lived a long vindictive process where the consequences have not been as important as it might seem. I had to skip a debate, largely ideological, that raises the reality of society, the path that social evolution has gone and the path that it should go. It will be established between the defenders of the liberal model (ideological - political) and new sectors that arise at this time. • Defenders: All this imbalance that is taking place is not a direct consequence of the liberal process itself. The problem or fault lies in the numerous obstacles, obstacles and resistance that still exist to carry out such a process to its ultimate consequences.

- Critics: They absolutely do not agree with these assessments Utopian Socialists (some author called them Romantic Socialists), stand out within this current Owen, Fourier or Saint Simon among others.

The utopians also start from some of the ideas of the 18th century, but unquestionably their theoretical elaboration, their theoretical discourse is directly linked to the process of implantation and development of the capitalist system and the consequences emanating from its development. They set themselves the objective of demonstrating that the capitalist system is an unfair system, not only this, but also that it leads to results contrary to those that its defenders proclaim. They attack one of the great principles of classical liberalism - Individualism, they fight the idea that strength is in individual interest and free competition.

OWEN: "The first and most necessary object of all existence is happiness, but happiness cannot be obtained individually, it is useless to expect a bound happiness, we must all take part in it or at most they will never accept it."

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The utopians return to the idea that man is a social being by nature - Communal = communism, think that now that the age of reason has entered, all logical, reasonable and reasoned arguments should be accepted without further problem, because they are on your side. The most prepared, cultured people with a certain responsibility will be able to understand these sectors and never the popular masses. Understanding that once the problem is seen, measures will be taken against these evils.

There are a series of pilot experiences such as the creation of associations and cooperatives where the worker will have a greater role. It tries to show that benefits can be maintained but these will not revert to the employer but to the workers - Distribution of wealth and benefits. They will have a rather reduced influence on the working class itself, precisely because their theses are not directed at them.

Important role for his criticism of society and existing capitalism from which later theories were developed.

- 1848: The trigger will be the crisis that has lasted since 1846 and culminated in the year 1848 itself (hugely complex).

LABROUSSE: It showed that in 1946 the last subsistence crisis of the old system (AR) was produced, parallel to that crisis there was also a crisis of overproduction of the new capitalist and individualized system.

Started in Ireland (bad potato harvest), Flanders and France among others. Where there is a food shortage and a lower purchasing power due to the consequent increase in prices. It is a revolution driven on the one hand by the lack of food and consequent hunger and, on the other by the crisis of overproduction that lowers the prices of manufactured products and therefore increases unemployment. The bourgeois classes coincide in this revolutionary wave, advocating greater openness and fewer obstacles, that is, the total disappearance of the structures of the Old Regime, the popular sectors moved by hunger and layoffs, and the middle sectors that are beginning to develop in these moments.

JANUARY 1848: ITALIAN PENINSULA - SICILY and MILAN.

FEBRUARY 1848: PARIS (FRANCE).

MARCH 1848: VIENNA (AUSTRIA - HUNGARY).

ITALIAN PENINSULA - TURIN, PARMA and MODENA.

GERMANY.

SPAIN.

PORTUGAL.

SCANDINAVIAN COUNTRIES.

ENGLAND: Moment of greatest virulence of the Chartist movement.

This wave is of great importance since various sectors and objectives come together, coming together in their demands.

IMPACT

- Consolidation of the bourgeois liberal system (case of France - model of universal suffrage. With exceptions, as is the case of Russia. Generally, moderate constitutional monarchical models will be extended).
- Definitive rupture between the bourgeoisie and the working class - labor movement (Marx - in 1848 writes the "Communist Manifesto", vindication of workers' rights).
- Failure of nationalism (Italy and Germany, fail to establish themselves as unified states).
- Failure of the labor sectors, which in their aspirations, claims and objectives will be disappointed, by a settled bourgeoisie that intends to preserve what has been achieved, that is, the system or model that it has managed to implement.

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